

grain yield from weedy plots, expressed as a proportion of yield from the clean-weeded plots, was negatively correlated with weed weight at rice maturity ($r = 0.62$, $n = 36$) and positively correlated with rice root length at 49 DAS (0.79), and tiller number (0.75) and leaf area (0.73) at 36 DAS. These results are further evidence of the association between crop development during its vegetative phase and competitiveness with weeds.

More studies will be conducted to confirm the factors that determine differences among eleven cultivars in weed competitiveness. Promising cultivars will be used in a breeding program and further evaluated for yield potential. ■

Stress tolerance—drought

Genetic variability of osmotic adjustment under drought stress in rice

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Drought is the major abiotic stress limiting rice yield in the rainfed lowland and upland ecosystems. Little progress has been made in incorporating tolerance for drought into rice. Understanding the physiological mechanism and their genetic basis will be helpful in developing selection strategies for improving drought tolerance in rice.

Osmotic adjustment as a process of active solute accumulation under drought stress is receiving increasing attention as an important component of drought tolerance in crop plants (Blum 1989, Ludlow and Muchow 1990). Osmotic adjustment results from the accumulation of solutes within cells, which lowers the osmotic potential and helps maintain turgor of both shoots and roots as plants experience water deficit stress. By using osmotic adjustment as a trait in dryland crop breeding programs, prospects are good for increasing potential yield and stabilizing yield under drought, as demonstrated in wheat (Morgan and

Condon 1986) and sorghum (Ludlow et al 1990).

The objective of our study was to identify the extent of genetic variation for osmotic adjustment in cultivated rice grown under drought stress. Twelve cultivars representing a range of germplasm from traditional dryland types to improved rainfed lowland types were studied under greenhouse conditions. Plants were grown in large PVC containers using a potting soil mixture. Water was withheld from 50 d after sowing to induce drought stress.

Changes in leaf osmotic potential and relative water content were measured every other day from initiation of stress until the plants wilted. The entire drought period was about 35 d. Osmotic adjustment was calculated following the method described by Morgan (1992). Results indicated large genetic variation for osmotic adjustment among the cultivars. The cultivar IR62266 expressed higher osmotic adjustment (1.76 MPa) than the rest. The cultivars Azucena, CT9993, Moroberekan, and IR52561 showed lower osmotic adjustment with values of 0.86, 0.81, 0.80, and 0.50 MPa, respectively.

Despite the positive influence of osmotic adjustment as a drought tolerance mechanism, the adoption of this trait in breeding programs for crop improvement has been slow. Among other reasons, the inability to rapidly and precisely screen large breeding populations for osmotic adjustment limits progress toward using this trait as a selection criterion. Screening for osmotic adjustment currently requires time-consuming complex measurement procedures. Identifying molecular markers (such as restriction fragment length polymorphism) linked to osmotic adjustment may provide plant breeders with a new tool for selecting cultivars with higher osmotic adjustment capacity.

The present study showed large genetic variation for osmotic adjustment that offers a good possibility for identifying suitable molecular markers for this trait in rice. Some of the genotypes tested in the study are parents of recombinant inbred and doubled-haploid line mapping populations that are being developed in collaboration with IRRI scientists for tagging genes associated with drought-adaptive traits.

Cited references

- Blum A. 1989. Osmotic adjustment and growth of barley genotypes under drought stress. *Crop Sci.* 29:230-233.
- Ludlow M, Muchow RC. 1990. A critical evaluation of the traits for improving crop yields in water-limited environments. *Adv. Agron.* 43:107-153.
- Ludlow MM, Santamaria FJ, Fukai S. 1990. contribution of osmotic adjustment to grain yield of *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench under water-limited conditions. II. Water stress after anthesis. *Aust. J. Agric. Res.* 41:67-78.
- Morgan JM. 1992. Osmotic components and properties associated with genotypic differences in osmoregulation in wheat. *Aust. J. Plant Physiol.* 19:67-76.
- Morgan JM, Condon AG. 1986. Water use, grain yield, and osmoregulation in wheat. *Aust. J. Plant Physiol.* 13:523-532. ■

Stress tolerance—excess water

Characterization of the pyruvate decarboxylase gene family of rice and its potential application to submergence tolerance

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Flash flooding is one of the major causes of mass destruction of rice in many countries in Southeast Asia. Flooding produces anaerobic conditions because gases diffuse more slowly in water than in air.

Under anoxia, alcoholic fermentation occurs at rapid rates during submergence. In maize, the two key enzymes, pyruvate decarboxylase (PDC) and alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH), show higher activities under anoxia (Baily-Serres et al 1988). Only minimal levels of ADH are required for ethanol production in maize

Genomic organization of three rice *pdc* genes, the cDNAs, and their expression in response to aerobic and anaerobic conditions. +++ = high induction, ++ = moderate anaerobic induction. UTR = untranslated region.

root tips (Roberts et al 1989). This permits survival under hypoxic (2-4% oxygen) conditions, suggesting a key regulatory role for PDC under anoxia. Furthermore, in maize roots under anoxia, the rate of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis and cytoplasmic pH control are more important in determining survival than are the actual levels of ATP or the energy charge (Xia et al 1995). It would therefore appear that a further enhancement in the activity of PDC should increase the production of ethanol and increase the rate of ATP synthesis under anoxia.

We are cloning *pdc* and *adh* genes from rice. Three genomic clones, *pdc1*, *pdc2*, and *pdc3* (Hossain et al 1994a), and two cDNA clones that correspond to *pdc1* (Hossain et al 1994b) and *pdc2* (Huq et al 1995) genomic clones, respectively, of the *pdc* gene family have been isolated, sequenced, and characterized from rice (IR54) (see figure).

Comparison of the deduced amino acid sequences of the three rice *pdc* genes showed that *pdc1* and *pdc2* are 88% similar and 78% identical, *pdc1* and *pdc3* are 89% similar and 79% identical, and *pdc2* and *pdc3* are 89% similar and 79% identical. The maize *pdc* (Kelley 1989) showed similarity and identity values of 95% and 90% to rice *pdc1*, 88% and 79% to rice *pdc2*, and 90% and 81% to rice *pdc3*. At least four bands were observed from a Southern blot of IR54 genomic DNA when probed with a DNA fragment from the *pdc* coding region. Southern blots with probes specific to the 5' and 3' untranslated regions of differential bands of these cDNAs showed differential bands corresponding to these genes.

Transgenic rice plants with introduced *pdc* construct confirmed by PCR and Southern analysis. Plasmids used were *pdc 29:35S promoter-adh intron-sense pdc cDNA1-nos*; *pdc 32:35S promoter-adh intron-antisense pdc cDNA1-nos*; *pdc 38:actin promoter-sense pdc cDNA1-nos*; *pdc 40:actin promoter-antisense pdc cDNA1-nos*; *pdc 42:6xARE promoter-adh intron-sense pdc cDNA1-nos*; and *pdc 44:6xARE promoter-adh intron-antisense pdc cDNA1-nos*.

Genotype trans-formed	Plasmids	Positive plants (no.)	Fertility
IR54	<i>pdc 38</i>	6	Fertile
	<i>pdc 40</i>	2	Fertile
	<i>pdc 29</i>	20	Fertile
	<i>pdc 42</i>	4	3 fertile/1 sterile
Radon	<i>pdc 42</i>	8	8 sterile
	<i>pdc 44</i>	15	3 fertile/12 sterile
	<i>pdc 32</i>	2	Fertile
	<i>pdc 38</i>	4	1 fertile/3 sterile

Northern blotting experiments showed that the *pdc1* and *pdc2* are inducible under anaerobic conditions; *pdc3* did not give any detectable band on a Northern blot. Unlike *pdc1* and *pdc2* genes, *pdc3* does not have any introns and is shorter; it is probably a pseudogene. The *pdc1* promoter has multiple copies of anaerobic responsive-like elements as in the maize *adh* gene.

Deletion analysis of the *pdc1* promoter driving the *gusA* reporter gene was performed to evaluate the anaerobic responsive elements in transformed rice protoplasts. Following incubation under aerobic and anaerobic conditions, transient GUS activity assays indicated the presence of both positive and negative regulatory sequences.

Six plasmid constructs have been made using the rice actin promoter, CaMV35S promoter, and 6XARE (anaerobic responsive element) promoter driving the *pdc* cDNA1 gene in both the sense and the antisense orientations. All of these plasmids have been transformed into rice cells by the biolistic or PEG uptake method (see table). For certain constructs, although many hygromycin-resistant calli were selected and regenerated small plantlets, they failed to grow to maturity. Some of the IR54 transgenic plants did have normal morphological appearance (height, tiller number, seed set) compared with seed-grown plants, but most of the Radon transgenic plants were sterile or produced only a few seeds. Further characterization

of transgenic plants, segregation of the transgenes in the progeny, and their response under submerged conditions are under investigation.

Cited references

- Baily-Serres J, Kloeckener-Gruissem B, Freeling M. 1988. Genetic and molecular approaches to the study of the anaerobic response and tissue-specific gene expression in maize. *Plant Cell Environ.* 11:351-355.
- Hossain MA, Huq E, Hodges TK. 1994b. Sequence of cDNA from *Oryza sativa* L. encoding *pyruvate decarboxylase 1* gene. *Plant Physiol.* 106:799-800.
- Hossain MA, McGee JD, Grover A, Dennis ES, Peacock WJ, Hodges TK. 1994a. Nucleotide sequence of a rice genomic *pyruvate decarboxylase* gene that lacks introns: a pseudo-gene? *Plant Physiol.* 106:1697-1698.
- Huq E, Hossain MA, Hodges TK. 1995. Cloning and sequencing of cDNA encoding *pyruvate decarboxylase 2*, gene from rice. *Plant Physiol.* (in press)
- Kelley PM. 1989. Maize pyruvate decarboxylase mRNA is induced anaerobically. *Plant Mol. Biol.* 13:213-222.
- Roberts JKM, Chang K, Webster C, Callis C, Walbot V. 1989. Dependence of ethanol fermentation, cytoplasmic pH regulation, and viability on the activity of alcohol dehydrogenase in hypoxic maize root tips. *Plant Physiol.* 89:1275-1278.
- Xia, J-H, Saglio P, Roberts JKM. 1995. Nucleotide levels do not critically determine survival of maize root tips acclimated to a low-oxygen environment. *Plant Physiol.* 108:589-595. ■

Molecular implication of submergence tolerance in rice using expressed sequence tags as probes

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Large-scale sequencing of randomly selected cDNA clones was done to investigate feasibility of a method for isolating plant genes. Total RNA used for cDNA synthesis was prepared from suspension cultured cells of rice grown